

Microscopic Aspects of Force in Quantum Mechanics

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. and S.P.N. Messina, Nov. 12, 2019

In a previous note (1), it was shown that by taking the derivative of the time-independent Schrodinger equation in the form: $-1/2m (d/dx d/dx W / W) + V(r)=E$ yields an equation linking various fluxes to $-d/dx V$ i.e. force. In other notes, it was shown the time-independent Schrodinger equation may be written microscopically for each p momentum plane wave as:

$$p^2/2m f(p) + \text{Sum } j+k=p V_j f(k) = E f(p) \quad ((1))$$

Here, the same E (energy) applies to all p momentum waves. Thus, it is as if there is a dynamical resonance for each p wave, with various k momentum waves combining with the potential ($V_j =$ the j th Fourier transform of $V(r)$) to form a p momentum wave. In this note, we wish to examine force microscopically in terms of ((1)) and also to consider the effects of noninertial frames or constrained motion on microscopic force.

Conditional Average Picture

In a set of previous notes, it was argued the time-independent Schrodinger equation is based on complex conditional probability i.e. $P(p/x) = f(p)\exp(ipx) / W(x)$ ((2)) where $W(x)$, the wavefunction = $\text{Sum over } p f(p) \exp(ipx)$. Thus, it seems there is a two channel physical system, with the channels linked in a periodic manner. Using the unusual conditional probability ((2)), one may calculate the quantum average of various functions, including $p^2/2m$ which yields an average quantum kinetic energy at a point x . This quantum average kinetic energy when added to $V(x)$, the potential which appears in classical physics, yields a constant energy E at each x . Thus, the time-independent Schrodinger equation is equivalent to:

$$-1/2m d/dx d/dx W / W + V(r) = E \quad ((3))$$

Taking the spatial derivative of ((3)) yields an equation for force in terms of quantum averages and fluxes, namely:

$$-1/2m (d/dx)^3 W / W - (-1/2m d/dx d/dx W/W) (d/dx W / W) = \text{Force}(x) = -d/dx V \quad ((4))$$

$d/dx W / W$ is a quantum momentum flux average. In the form ((4)), classical force appears to be related to the quantum average of p^3 minus a product of kinetic energy at point x times a momentum flux.

Microscopic Momentum Picture

In a previous note (2), it is argued one may write the time-independent Schrodinger equation for each momentum wave in terms of the resonance which is occurring, i.e. ((1))

$$p^2/2m f(p) + \text{Sum } j+k=p V_j f(k) = E f(p) \quad \text{where } V_j \text{ is the } j\text{th Fourier transform of } V(r)$$

Thus, it seems the energy E which is common to all momentum values is the resonance driver in equation ((1)). Different k momentum waves scatter with the potential to create a p wave in such a way that when added to $p^2/2m f(p)$ one obtains $E f(p)$. This has the appearance of a dynamic resonance. A question which arises, however, is how is force manifested in such a microscopic picture?

First, one may note ((1)) is obtained by writing the time-independent Schrodinger in terms of a Fourier series for W and V . Next, the coefficients of each $\exp(ikx)$ are set to zero, because $\exp(ikx)$ represents a linearly independent basis. Thus, one obtains ((1)) which holds at each point x , i.e. the resonance is really in momentum space.

One may ask how $\exp(ipx)$ changes as one moves from x to $x+b$, where b is infinitesimal? The change is:

$$ibp \exp(ipx) \quad ((5))$$

Thus, the change in:

$$\exp(ipx) (p^2/2m f(p) + \sum_{j+k=p} V_j f(k) - E f(p)) = 0 \text{ as one moves from } x \text{ to } x+b \text{ is:}$$

$$p (p^2/2m f(p) + \sum_{j+k=p} V_j f(k) - E f(p)) = 0 \quad ((6))$$

The change is the original equation multiplied by p . One may in fact divide out p .

Equation ((6)) may be considered in a different manner. Consider:

$$(-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} - E) W + VW = 0 \quad ((7))$$

Taking the derivative of ((7)), using Fourier series and collecting coefficients of $\exp(ipx)$ yields:

$$p(p^2/2m - E) f(p) + \sum_{k+j=p} k V_k f(j) + \sum_{k+j=p} V_k f(j) = 0 \quad \text{or}$$

$$p(p^2/2m - E) f(p) + p \sum_{k+j=p} V_k f(j) = 0$$

Thus, ((6)) is obtained. Thus, the extra p appears due to the properties of translation of $\exp(ipx)$ and disappears in an equation for a single p wave. If one sums over all p waves i.e. multiplies ((6)) by $\exp(ipx)$, divides by W and sums over p , the extra p from translation does not disappear, but contributes to what one calls 'force'. Thus ((4)) may be obtained.

$$-1/2m (\frac{d}{dx})^3 W / W - (-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W/W) (\frac{d}{dx} W / W) = \text{Force}(x) = -\frac{d}{dx} V$$

((4)) seems to be a macroscopic equation in that it separates out fluxes, although the first term is microscopic. In ((6)), however, one is able to consider force, i.e. the extra p term in the resonance equation for a single p wave. For this single p wave resonance, the extra momentum factor does not do anything. The basic quantum bound state resonance still occurs whether one moves from one point x to another. It seems that it is the relative spatial transformation property of $\exp(ip_1 x)$ and $\exp(ip_2 x)$ which brings in the idea of force through an average.

Noninertial Frames or Constrained Motion

In a previous note (3), the idea of constrained motion or a noninertial frame was considered. For the case of a dilation in the direction r where $r^2 = x^2 + y^2$

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r \frac{dW}{dr} \right) + V(r)W - Cr \frac{dW}{dr} = E W \quad ((8))$$

(Here C is imaginary and one may ultimately write W as W_1 times a phase factor.)

Force in such a case was considered in terms of average fluxes, just as in ((4)). Here, we wish to consider force in microscopic terms. Let $W = R(r)A(a)$ where a is the angle.

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r \frac{dW}{dr} \right) + \frac{d}{dr} \left(\frac{dW}{dr} \right) \right) - \frac{1}{2m} \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{d}{da} \left(r \frac{dW}{da} \right) + Cr \frac{d}{dr} W + V(r)W = E W \quad ((9))$$

Thus, one obtains: $\frac{d}{da} \left(\frac{dW}{da} \right) / W = C^2$ and

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \left(r \frac{d}{dr} W + r^2 \frac{d}{dr} \left(\frac{dW}{dr} \right) \right) + Cr^3 \frac{d}{dr} \left(\frac{R}{R} \right) + r^2 V - E r^2 = C^2 \quad ((9b))$$

. It would be interesting if one could find a series expansion for W and V which would behave in a similar manner to the Fourier series in one dimension. It is possible that the Fourier-Bessel series serve this purpose

$$W = \sum_n c_n J_0(z_n/L r) \quad \text{and} \quad (Cr^3 \frac{d}{dr} \left(\frac{R}{R} \right) + r^2 V - E r^2) = \sum_n d_n J_0(z_n/L r)$$

It seems that $\left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} + \frac{d}{dr} \left(\frac{d}{dr} \right) \right) J_0(z_j/L r) = (z_j/L)^2 J_0(z_j/L r)$ (5) so this may be analogous to the one dimensional Fourier $\exp(ipx)$ series case. In this case, the independent basis function is $J_0(z_j/L r)$. Thus for a given z_j/L (i.e. zero of the Bessel function):

$$r^2 \left(-\frac{1}{2m} (z_j/L)^2 - E \right) c_j + B_j = 0 \quad \text{where } B_j \text{ is the } j\text{th term of the } J_0(z_j/L r) \text{ expansion of } (Cr^3 \frac{d}{dr} \left(\frac{R}{R} \right) + r^2 V - E r^2). \text{ One may divide out } r^2.$$

One may argue this represents a resonance because a unique E value is present for all z_j/L values.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have tried to argue that for the time-independent Schrodinger equation, a resonance equation exists for each p momentum plane wave. This equation depends on a single E (total energy) for all p momentum waves. The equation is independent of x, and is obtained by performing a one dimensional Fourier series expansion of the Schrodinger equation and equating coefficients of $\exp(ipx)$ to 0 due to the linear independence of the basis. If one translates an $\exp(ipx)$ from x to $x+b$ where b is infinitesimal one obtains the same resonance equation multiplied by p. This p can be divided out and the single p momentum level and so does not seem to affect the resonance. For different $\exp(ikx)$, however, one has different k values, so if one averages the translational shift, the k (momentum) remains and gives rise to 'force'. Thus, force, seems to arise because the translational shift of $\exp(ikx)$ differs from one k to another when one takes an average. Force does not seem to be felt at single momentum value level, but rather seems to be an average idea.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Fluxes in Quantum Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2019)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. 2x2 Matrix Model and the Schrodinger Equation (preprint, zenodo, 2018)
3. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Quantum Flux and Force in a Rotating Frame (preprint, zenodo, 2019)
4. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fourier%E2%80%93Bessel_series
5. Fourier Bessel Series and Boundary Value Problems in Cylindrical Coordinates
<http://faculty.fiu.edu/~meziani/Note12.pdf>